
**THE FEATURES OF SPEECH ACTIVITY DEVELOPMENT AND FORMATION
WITH THE DICTIONARY OF PROFESSIONAL VOCABULARY STUDENTS
OF NON-LINGUISTIC SPECIALTIES.**

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Annotation

The article discusses an example of training foreign language for students of non-linguistic specialties. Professional orientation of teaching foreign languages to student non-linguistic specialties is aimed at training a highly qualified specialist who masters all aspects of speech activity in foreign language. An important aspect of professionally oriented foreign language teaching language for students of non-linguistic specialties is the formation of a professional vocabulary.

Key words

professional education, university students, medical students, methodology of English language, Competency Approach.

In the modern world, a qualified specialist must have knowledge not only in their professional field, but also in other areas, including speak a foreign language. Proficiency in a foreign language is still essential at school, therefore the task of subsequent vocational educational institutions develop and deepen this knowledge. The article discusses an example of training foreign language for students of non-linguistic specialties. Professional orientation of teaching foreign languages to students non-linguistic specialties is aimed at training a highly qualified specialist who masters all aspects of speech activity in foreign language:

1. Speaking, which includes dialogic speech as the ability to conduct a conversation on professional topics and monologue speech as the ability to express your point of view and be able to argue for it.

2. Learning to read involves reading with previously removed difficulties and reading that requires overcoming difficulties with the help of lexical, grammatical and semantic analysis, as well as translation. Therefore it is possible use special pre-text tasks aimed at mastering the techniques of penetrating into the content of what

is being read and revealing the meaning unlearned words and recognition of complex grammatical structures.

3. Writing, as the ability to express a thought graphically, in professionally oriented training can be used as a translation of specialized literature, drawing up annotations, summarizing, technical specifications, instructions, business letters and so on.

4. Learning to listen as the ability to perceive and understand an interlocutor orally, on a specific topic or situation. An important aspect of professionally oriented foreign language teaching language for students of non-linguistic specialties is the formation of a professional vocabulary. In this case, the teacher may encounter a problem lack of awareness in a certain professional field, therefore, joint work with teachers of specialized disciplines is important; with their recommendations, topics are developed and adjusted content of work programs. Practical application of professional vocabulary is carried to "specialty weeks", various language events, involvement and collaboration with additional language organizations, participation in competitions, conferences, and seminars.

Training tasks of the international competition World are also used

Skills, for example, in the "Electrical Installation" competency, which allows you to develop interest in both the chosen profession and in learning a foreign language. Work on such lexical units involve the simultaneous development of pronunciation skills on the material of isolated words on the topic of sentences, including new words. After completing each topic, vocabulary knowledge has checked by oral questioning, interview, translation and retelling of text, performing exercises, etc. This creates motivation to study professional vocabulary, train translation skills, structure professional vocabulary by topic.

Control in teaching a foreign language plays an important role and forms an integral part of the educational process. Control is necessary to identify problems, determining the degree of proficiency in the target language and adjusting further training. To determine appropriate forms of control it is advisable to pay increased attention to individual abilities each student, diagnose what have achieved, and if something is not it happened, then why. Pollution of the natural environment is b traditionally controlled by physic-chemical, physical and chemical methods analysis of air, water, soil, biological objects and comparison of the content of pollutants in these objects with background concentrations or established hygienic standards. The development of the ecological situation on Earth in recent decades has shown that hygienic standards developed to protect human health in most cases do not ensure the preservation and survival of many plant species (lichens,

mosses, conifers) and the normal functioning of many ecosystems. Existing physical and chemical methods for analyzing environmental objects for the content of pollutants, and especially on the most dangerous pollutants (heavy metals, pesticides, dioxins, etc.) are not only extremely complex and time-consuming, but also require large financial costs. At the same time, despite the high accuracy of determining elements and compounds in samples, the results of these analyzes are not sufficiently reliable from an environmental point of view for the following reasons:

- the content of pollutants in the objects of analysis never mathematically corresponds to the product of doses and time due to their migration and redistribution in objects and the environment;

- content (accumulation) of harmful substances in objects varies greatly from year to year, even if their emissions or content in the atmosphere is constant due to the instability of weather and climate conditions; the results of short-term chemical and physicochemical methods cannot provide a correct ecological assessment of the long-term effect of pollutants on ecosystems.

A characteristic feature of modern science is the creation of new methods at the junctions of various related fields of science. An example is the development of biological methods of analysis based on the achievements of such areas of biology as microbiology, zoology, botany, etc. The use of biological methods allows:

- simultaneously register environmental pollution by various substances from a low level (below sanitary and hygienic MPC) to critically dangerous levels over large areas;

- carry out ecological zoning of vast territories (metropolis, district, region) according to pollution levels and the state of vegetation;

- assess the environmental hazard of different levels of air pollution for biota in general and vegetation in particular;

- determine critical levels of chemical pollutant load for terrestrial ecosystems.

Important advantages of biological methods are their simplicity, the absence of expensive and complex equipment necessary for the use of traditional physicochemical methods and physical methods. They do not require sample preparation and isolation of a specific compound; they allow analysis water, soil and air in expeditionary conditions directly at the sampling site. They are used to assess the degree of general pollution and general toxicity of the environmental object for living organisms and the expediency of its further detailed analysis by other, more complex and costly, methods.

The quality of the environment, the degree of its pollution are judged by the species composition, the ratio of species or the state of individual species in the ecosystem (bio indication methods) or by the reactions of laboratory experimental organisms placed in the studied medium (methods of bio testing). These organisms must have known and measurable characteristics, easy to cultivate in the laboratory.

Biological methods are based on the fact that for life activity - growth, reproduction and functioning of living organisms - an environment of a strictly defined chemical environment is necessary composition. When the chemical composition of the habitat changes, the body after some time, sometimes almost immediately, will give appropriate response signal. All substances in relation to living organisms is conditionally divided:

- 1) into vital;
- 2) toxic;
- 3) Physiologically inactive.

Obviously, only the first two cases, a relatively quick reaction of the body can be expected. Physiologically inactive substances can only give remote result. Monitoring the level of pollution of environmental objects can be carried out on almost any species, from viruses and microorganisms to humans, and on all levels of organization of living matter from molecular to ecosystem. Historically, an anthropocentric approach has been outlined in solving the problems of environmental quality regulation. However, the preservation of the environment for a safe human life is possible only if the necessary ecological regime is ensured for the entire biota and the biosphere as a whole. To maintain biogeochemical cycles in the biosphere and its homeostasis it is necessary first of all to provide optimal conditions for the activities of producers (vegetation). This is important because they are at the beginning of the trophic chain and the cycle of matter and energy in the biosphere depends on their productivity.

In the face of global air, water and soil pollution it is no longer possible to talk about the absolute quality of environmental objects and, perhaps, even about their pre-anthropogenic quality or the natural biogeochemical background of pollutants. Since the necessity of dialectical unity and a kind of compromise in the evolution of human society and nature in the conditions of techno genesis is recognized, the quality of the environment should be considered as optimally acceptable, necessary for the preservation and development of civilization and the biosphere. Therefore, the acceptable quality of the environment in modern conditions should be recognized as such (composition, properties, purity), which does not cause

perceptible disturbances in the functioning of organisms, ecosystems and biogeochemical cycles of the biosphere.

Methods bio indications make it possible to obtain an integral assessment of the quality of environmental objects for living organisms, to identify critical load levels of chemical pollutants for terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems.

The quality of the environment, the degree of its pollution are judged by the species composition, ratio of species and the state of individual species in

ecosystem, accumulation in the biomass of some species of various substances (heavy metals, pesticides, radionuclides, nitrates, etc.). It should be noted that a binary lesson is a non-traditional type of lesson that can be taught by two or more subject teachers. Binary is a model for the implementation of interdisciplinary connections and integration of subjects, allowing connect subjects such as English and biology. When conducting binary lessons, high motivation is developed, and control of the students being studied disciplines proceeds in an unobtrusive form. It is known that the formation of written speech competence is included into the curriculum as one of the goals of teaching the discipline "Foreign Language" at the university. However, teachers often do not devote enough attention to written language. attention in the educational process, while limiting itself to the formation of certain types of competencies, namely functional skills (letter writing and essays) and academic writing. This choice of teachers is determined by pragmatic objectives, the content of programs and international exams.

However, the forms and learning potential of writing are much more variable. For example, creative writing can be successfully used to formation of dialogue skills characteristic of oral speech: write a detective story with dialogue or a theatrical play, which later can be played in the audience. We are convinced that written language plays no less important role than oral speech in the process of teaching a foreign language, since the development of competent, well-structured oral speech is impossible without systematic work on different types of writing.

Thus, the professional orientation of foreign language teaching language for students of non-linguistic specialties is a multi-level, integrated, continuous system of interaction between all participants in the educational process, the goal of which is the formation of competent, professionally in demand, educated specialist.

LITERATURE:

1. Abaeva F. B. Practice-oriented approach to teaching foreign languages language of master's students - future teachers // Baltic Humanitarian Journal. - 2015. - No. 4 (13). - P. 58-61.
2. Zubkov A. D., Morozova M. A. Teaching special vocabulary using the material of authentic corporate Internet resources [Text] / A. D. Zubkov, M. A. Morozova // Open and distance education. - 2017. - No. 1(65). - P. 12-19.
3. Denisova E. V. Professionally oriented approach to teaching a foreign language (pedagogical concept) // Pedagogical mastery: materials of the IV International. scientific conf. (Moscow, February 2014). - M.: BukiVedi, 2014. - pp. 198-203.
4. Kucheryavaya T. L. Working with lexical material in the study of professionally oriented English [Text] // Current problems of pedagogy: materials of the VII International. scientific conf. (Chita, April 2016).
5. Makhaeva A.K. Professionally oriented level of foreign language teaching in a non-linguistic university // Young scientist. - 2015. - No. 23. - pp. 979-982. - URL <https://moluch.ru/archive/103/23896/> (Access date: 10/04/2019)
6. Esonovna, A. S. (2020). Linguistic features of Latin and Greek synonymous morphemes in the lexical system of the french language. International scientific review, (LXXII), 47-48.
7. Abrayeva, S. (2022). Lotin tilining tibbiyot terminologiyasida roli (Doctoral dissertation, Uzbekistan, Tashkent).
8. Esonovna, A. S. (2023). TIBBIYOT TERMINOLOGIYASIDA LOTIN VA YUNON TILLARINING AHAMIYATI.
9. Esonovna, A. S. (2023). Substitution of Latin and Greek Morphemes in Words in Medical Terminology. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 4(2), 32-34. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/9P4FD>